

THE SUPERVISORY SKILLS OF SCHOOL ADMINISTRATORS IN THE DISTRICT OF DUMANJUG II: ENHANCEMENT TRAINING DESIGN

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The Supervisory Skills of School Administrators in the District of Dumanjug II: Enhancement Training Design

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Abstract

This research study aimed to assess the supervisory skills of public elementary and secondary school administrators in the District of Dumanjug II, Division of Cebu Province during the School Year 2022-2023 as basis for an Enhancement Training Design. This study utilized the Descriptive Normative Method using the survey questionnaires to the 351 teachers and 20 school principals. On the respondents' profile, majority are above 45 years having a percentage of seventy-five. In terms of gender, most of them were female comprising 65 percent. Concerning civil status, most of the subjects were married comprising 90 percent. There were only two or 10 percent of principals who earned units in Doctor of Education- CAR. There are nine or 45 percent who were School Principals/ Head Teacher. Eleven were district coordinators comprising fifty-five percent. Most of the principals have attended trainings and seminars with the average frequency of 55 percent and had teaching experiences more than 25 years and above comprising six or 30 percent. This study shows that most principals have a Moderately Proficient level of supervisory skills obtained an overall score of (2.95, 2.6, 2.6, 3.34, 2.76, 3.23, 2.76, 3.23). Statistically, there is no significant difference (0.213, 0.892, 0.356, 0.261, 0.351, 0.881) between the principals' and teachers' perception towards the principals' supervisory skills. Also, there was a significant relationship which obtained a p-value of (0.032, 0.9, 0.226, 0.511, 0.353, 0.173, 0.335, 0.884) in terms of the different aspects with respect to the different criteria. Based on the findings, it can be concluded that the level of supervisory skills of the principals is viewed as effective based on the principals' perspective, but it is viewed as low based on the teachers' perspective. With the foregoing findings, it is prescribe that principals must continue to improve their supervisory skills. Hence, an "ENHANCEMENT TRAINING DESIGN" is recommended.

Keywords: administration and supervision, school administrators' supervisory skills, descriptive survey method

Introduction

From the viewpoint tasks of education, a principal deals a significant role in every school. The gains and losses of the school lie on every principal's shoulder. The vital functions of the principal are educational manager, administrative planner, and instructional supervisor. In this endeavor, the principal must appear in professional courtesy, compassion, helpfulness, and consideration for teachers and other staff.

Section 7 of Republic Act 9155 enumerated that the multifarious task of every school principal is that the principal as an institutional supervisor shall lead in all educational activities and programs. Principals should not be restricted to their offices but should be present in the classrooms where the action is. Since principals are responsible for overseeing everything that occurs in the school, they should be making the rounds, asking about the needs of the instructors, sensing their shortcomings, sharing their happiness, and expressing sympathy for their sorrow. The principals must be able to make plans come to pass and the department's goal come to pass. Moreover, in order to fully realize the potential of the young children, we must also fully realize the potential of the principals and instructors.

The Department of Education Manual of 2000 also enumerated the duties and responsibilities of school principals as follows, supervises all personnel in the school; provides leadership in the development and implementation of all programs in the school; promotes efficiency of teaching and learning in all classes through in-service trainings, observations, and visits; coordinates all services for the wholesome growth and development of all pupils and other personnel in the school; leads in the evaluation of achievements in the division.

DepEd has seen changes in education can only happen if the teachers are active. They should also be able to motivate the individuals underneath them by influencing them and winning their esteem people in authority.

Principals should be able to correct, to encourage, to set the standard and to live by example. The school's administration should also serve as the direct link to the community who will open the door for more stakeholders to invest in public education. They should be able to engage the local decision-makers, the private sector, the non-government organizations so that they can be their partners in achieving the school improvement plans.

Due to the principals' extensive responsibilities and supervisory positions, it is inherent upon by assessing the level of their conduct and keeping a close eye on them, you may help them develop the managerial abilities necessary to establish an efficient educational administration relationship that exist in-between things to do. They must be willing to consider the need for innovation and ongoing enhancement of all educational initiatives.

Hence, the researcher is determined to investigate how the principals perform their duties as viewed by their subordinates. The teachers'

perception on the supervisory skills of their respective principals will serve as check and balance on the real scenario inside the school and if the principals are really doing their job as efficient administrators.

Principals see themselves in a good way, but the teachers were not satisfied, and it is during the pandemic period the skills shown among supervisory skills are different. This is the foundation upon which the researcher would like to learn on the supervisory skills of the principals and teachers' performance as basis in crafting enhancement training design.

Research Questions

This study assessed the status of supervisory skills in public elementary and secondary school principals in the District of Dumanjug II, Division of Cebu Province during the school year 2022-2023 as bases for enhanced training design. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the public school principals in terms of?
 - 1.1. age and gender;
 - 1.2. civil status;
 - 1.3. highest educational attainment;
 - 1.4. academic rank;
 - 1.5. position held;
 - 1.6. relevant trainings attended; and
 - 1.7. years of managerial experience?
2. What is the level of supervisory skills of the principals as assessed by the principals themselves and by the teachers in terms of?
 - 2.1. curriculum and instructional supervision;
 - 2.2. organization and personnel management;
 - 2.3. planning, assessing, and reporting teaching learning outcomes;
 - 2.4. school plant, resources and facilities management;
 - 2.5. personal, social growth and professional development;
 - 2.6. school, community linkages and public relation?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the assessment of the principal and the teacher respondents on the level of supervisory skills of the principals in terms of the different aspects?
4. Is there a significant relationship on the level of supervisory skills of the principals in terms of their profile?
5. Based on the results, what enhanced training design can be crafted?

Methodology

Research Design

The descriptive survey approach was used in this study to assess the supervisory skills of principals in public elementary and secondary schools in Cebu Province's Second District of Dumanjug. The objective is to ascertain whether there would be a significant difference in the principal and teacher respondents' assessments of the principals' level of supervisory skills in terms of the different aspects and if there will be a significant difference in the principals' level of supervisory skills in terms of their profiles.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were 20 principals and 351 teachers in the District of Dumanjug II, Dumanjug, Cebu located in southern part of Cebu as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. *Respondents of the Study*

<i>Name of Schools</i>	<i>District Of Dumanjug II</i>		<i>Administrators</i>		<i>Teachers</i>	
	<i>F</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
1. Bitoon Central School	1	5	36	10.26		
2. Tubod- Bitoon Elem.	1	5	14	3.99		
3. Kanyuko Elem. School	1	5	7	1.99		
4. Tangil Elem. School	1	5	19	5.41		
5. Panlaan Elem. School	1	5	11	3.13		
6. Kanghumaod ES	1	5	16	4.56		
7. Balaygtiki Elem. School	1	5	14	3.99		
8. Doldol Elem. School	1	5	8	2.28		
9. Manlapay Elem. School	1	5	7	1.99		
10. Bulak Elem. School	1	5	16	4.56		
11. Tubod- Dugoan ES	1	5	12	3.52		
12. Lamak Elem. School	1	5	4	1.11		
13. Pawa Elem. School	1	5	7	1.99		

14. Matalao Elem. School	1	5	7	1.99
15. Masa Elem. School	1	5	7	1.99
16. Cambanog Elem. School	1	5	7	1.99
17. Kanghalo Elem. School	1	5	2	0.57
18. Bitoon NVHS	1	5	108	30.77
19. Bulak NHS	1	5	35	9.97
20. Juancho and Placida Padayao NHS	1	5	14	3.99
Total	20	100	351	100

The District has seventeen (17) elementary schools, namely: the Bitoon Central School, the Tubod-Bitoon Elementary School, the Kanyuko Elementary School, the Tangil Elementary School, the Panlaan Elementary School, the Kanghumaod Elementary School, the Balaygtiki Elementary School, the Doldol

Elementary School, the Manlapay Elementary School, the Bulak Elementary School, the Tubod-Dugoan Elementary School, the Lamak Elementary School, Pawa Elementary School, the Matalao Elementary School, the Masa Elementary School, the Cambanog Elementary School and the Kanghalo Elementary School.

There are only three (3) secondary schools, including the Bitoon National Vocational High School, Bulak National High School, and Juancho and Placida Padayao National High School. There are twenty (20) primary and secondary schools in all. The respondents of the study will be the 351 teachers in schools belonging to Dumanjug District II, the research respondents and the 20 school administrators of participating schools.

Instrument

This study utilized a modified version of the questionnaire created by Sonny Valdez Matias, District of Rodriguez I and II, Division of Rizal (July 21, 2011). To determine the supervisory abilities of public elementary and secondary school principal's year 2022–2023, this research was conducted in the District of Dumanjug II, Division of Cebu Province.

The research questionnaire has 2 parts. The first part was to gather information about the respondents' profile with regards to age, sex, civil status, educational attainment, and managerial or educational experience. The profiling of respondents served as the grouping variables. The second section was used to assess how well principals/ school administrators can supervise staff members in terms of how they manage the administration and monitoring of the school. The school administrators rated each item on the scale of 1 to 5 with these interpretations: 5- Highly Proficient (HP), 4-Proficient (P), 3-Moderately Proficient (MP), 2-Slightly Proficient (SP), 1-Not Proficient (NP).

Procedure

The researcher observed some ethical principles in the conduct of the research. After the proposal, the researcher submitted his manuscript to the Cebu Technological University- Moalboal Campus Ethic Review Committee scrutinized the paper to validate that the research protocol done by the researcher has passed the standards imposed by the Research Ethics Committee. The researcher adhered to the research guidelines that were imposed by the committee before the actual conduct of the study.

When all the standards guidelines were complied by the researcher, he wrote a letter to the District Office of the Public Schools District Supervisor of Dumanjug II and endorsement to be forwarded to the Division Office of DepEd Cebu Province asking permission to the conduct of the study. When a letter has been approved, the researcher proceeded to send an online link to all public elementary and secondary schools for the survey. Consent forms were given to the respondents for them to review and sign if they would agree with the terms and conditions of the study.

The consent forms indicated that the participation is voluntary and no risks will be incurred if they choose not to participate. They could also withdraw or refuse to answer from the items from the tool.

The respondents were assured by the researcher that no information gathered will, in any way, divulged to anyone unless permission will be sought first from the authorities. Considering health and safety protocols, after the gathering of data, responses were tallied, analyzed, and interpreted objectively, and conclusions were drawn after.

Data Analysis

The frequency, percentage both rank with cross tabulation were used to determine the profile of respondents based on factors including age, sex, civil status, greatest level of education, duration of supervisory experience and administrative experience,

The Standard deviation and weighted mean were used to determine the degree of supervisory abilities of the principals as evaluated by the principals and by the teachers in terms of curriculum and instructional supervision, organization and personnel management, planning, assessing, and reporting teaching learning outcomes, management of the school's resources, plant, and facilities; and school, community links, and public relations.

The degree of supervisory abilities in terms of the various components was compared between the principal and teacher respondents'

judgments using the t-test to see if there is a statistically significant difference.

One-way ANOVA was utilized to find the significant differences between the principals' profiles in terms of their level of supervisory skills.

Results and Discussion

This section of the study presents the discussion of results on the data gathered based on variables considered in this study. The order of presentation is sequenced based on the specific problems raised in this study as indicated in Chapter I.

Respondents' Profile

The study involved elementary and secondary school principals, and their profiles were analyzed in terms of various factors such as age, gender, civil status, educational qualifications, academic rank, position held, relevant training attended, and years of administrative experience. The details are presented in Table 2.

Age

Age is one of the most important factors since the higher the directional age gap (younger supervisor-older employee dyad) between a supervisor and a subordinate, the lower the supervisor's employability ratings in comparison to the subordinates.

Based on the data, majority of the respondents were aged above 45 years above resulting to fifteen (15) and 75 percent while only a few were in the 31-45 years comprising four (4) or twenty percent only one (1) who aged in the mid 30's resulting to one (1) or five percent.

Table 2. Respondents' Profile

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
22-30	1	5
31-45	4	20
45 above	15	75
Total	20	100
Gender		
Male	7	35
Female	13	65
Total	20	100
Civil Status		
Single	1	5
Married	18	90
Widow	1	5
Total	20	100
Highest Educational Attainment		
EdD-CAR	2	10
MAED	8	40
MAED- CAR	7	35
MA Units	3	15
Total	20	100
Academic Rank		
School Principal	9	45
Assistant School Principal	2	10
Head Teacher	9	45
Total	20	100
Position Held		
District Coordinator	11	55
School Coordinator	7	35
Subject Coordinator	2	10
Total	20	100
Relevant Trainings Attended		
Project Gugma	2	10
Leadership Program	11	55
Virtual INSET	7	35
Total	20	100
Years of Managerial Experience		
25 and above	6	30
10-25	7	35
Below 10	7	35

	Total	20	100
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This is supported by Kunze and Menges (2017) on his study that if both supervisors and employees are less actively engaged in skill enhancement, older employees are more likely to develop narrow expertise, which limits their employability.

Supervisor willingness to invest in their employee also may decline, leading to a self-fulfilling prophecy with respect to supervisors' evaluation. Thus, age dissimilarity between supervisors and employees may also create a supervisory relationship which itself is a source of age stereotyping and decision-making. Status incongruence resulting from a supervisor who is younger than their subordinate potentially leads to age stereotyping of employees.

Gender

Teaching is a feminised profession in most parts of the world, but the proportion of principals is almost always lower than that of classroom practitioners. Gender is an important determiner of principals' skills in various pedagogies.

In terms of gender, most of the subjects were female comprising thirteen (13) or 65 percent and while only a few were male resulting seven (7) or thirty-five (35) percent.

It implies that the gender of both supervisors and subordinates affect the way interpersonal trust among workers elicit desirable organizational behaviors such as sharing responsibilities, sharing knowledge and other forms of citizenship behavior. Female supervisors need to build trust among their female employees before they can expect effective organizational behavior. The story is different for male supervisors and male employees. This has implications in the way male and female supervisors are trained. It also has implications for work group formation and composition.

Civil Status

Civil status, or marital status, are the distinct options that describe a person's relationship with a significant other and also a very important determiner.

Concerning civil status, most of the subjects were married comprising eighteen (18) or 90 percent while only a few were widowed or single both have one (1) response or 5 percent.

The principal takes the leadership responsibilities of the school. His actions, decisions and philosophies of leadership should be in consonance with the government's policies and programs and of the society in general in order that his school would continue to move forward incessantly. Anything the school head does and fails to do in the school all redounds to the entire organization.

Highest Educational Attainment

Highest educational attainment is a measure of the highest level of education that a person has completed. It can be classified into different categories based on the type and duration of the education program.

As revealed in the table, it could be seen that there were only two (2) or 10 percent of principals who earned units in Doctor of Education- Completed Academic Requirements (CAR), eight (8) or 40 percent who graduated Master of Arts in Education, seven (7) or thirty five percent who are MA.ED- CAR and there were three (3) or fifteen percent who started their masters' degree but they failed to complete the program.

There are elementary and secondary school heads with no units in the graduate level. This implies that they lack the necessary knowledge and skills on leadership and school management. It is assumed that a school head is highly competent so s/he can influence teaching by leadership and other skills. The school heads in the elementary and secondary are not educationally qualified their positions. Hence, they need to pursue graduate programs to equip them with knowledge and skills in effective school management.

This is supported by Phongphuttakun (2003) revealed that department heads' levels of job satisfaction were greater when administrators exhibited superior leadership conduct. With these conclusions, he suggested that master's or doctoral degrees and additional training be pursued to enhance the professional profiles of the teachers and heads of departments/schools.

Academic Rank

This part presents the distribution of the principals according to their field of specialization. As seen in the table, there are nine (9) or 45 percent who were School Principal and Head Teacher. While the least, comprising only two (2) or 10 percent of the respondents, the Assistant School Principal.

It implies that they must undergo principals' examination and encourage them to grow professionally. This is akin to the study of Daryanto (2020) states that the managerial functions of principals improve program implementation; supervising school activities, such as regulating activities, directing, and evaluating the implementation, guiding, and improving the staff ability. School effectiveness is associated with the quality of education. The belief behind school effectiveness is that all children must learn through the leadership the administrator. Therefore, the school head must grow continually in the profession to keep him abreast with the changes and demands in education so that he would perform his tasks and responsibilities as expected by the teaching and non-teaching force, stakeholders, and students in the best way he could.

Position Held

A position held refers to a specific role or job that an individual occupies within an organization, institution, or company. It encompasses the duties, responsibilities, authority, and level of seniority assigned to that person within their professional or organizational context.

As for their position held, eleven were district coordinators comprising fifty five (55) percent, seven (7) were school coordinators having a percentage of thirty five (35) percent and two (2) were subject coordinators resulting to ten (10) percent.

This is supported by Yuki (2009) that leadership is the time when a person holds a position of a leader, the power or ability to lead other people with his/ her capacity. It is a deliberate process of a person to emphasize a strong influence on others to guide, create a structure, as well as facilitate activities and relationships within a group or organization. The school head is believed to be continuously developing people, setting directions for the organization, and transforming the school into a more effective organization that fosters powerful teaching-learning (Primer on School Leadership, 2009). The school head is expected to be dynamic, innovative, and competent to promote and sustain quality education. The government through the Department of Education should consider the training needs of the school principals down to its minute details to fully capacitate them towards the full implementation of the program as it captures the whole educational system.

Relevant Training/s Attended

Trainings and Seminars are necessary for principals especially in today's environment to cope with the changing demands of the profession.

As revealed in the table, most of the principals have attended trainings and seminars with the average frequency of 55 percent who attended the Leadership Program, seven (7) or 35 percent who attended the Virtual Inset during pandemic time and two (2) or 10 percent who attended the Project Gugma training.

It implies that principals are not stagnant to new knowledge, and they have been equipped with new practices in education due to the Inservice Trainings that were initiated by the Department of Education (DepEd). This is akin to the study of Phongphuttakun (2003) stated that the schools should undertake trainings along these lines to involve not just the top managers/administrators but also the middle managers/administrators as well as instructors because the administrators have high leadership behavior and because there is still room for improvement to a very high degree.

Years of Administrative Experience

Administrative experience is acquired by working in positions with significant clerical duties. These roles involve communication, organization, research, scheduling, and office support skills. It may appear that every job includes some form of admin.

Based on the data, most of the principals had teaching experiences more than 25 years and above comprising six (6) or 30 percent, seven (7) or 35 percent had teaching experiences below 10-25 years.

School principals are the key leaders in our educational system. They are responsible of carrying out the school vision and mission. School Principals play integral roles in making schools function smoothly. They are involved in all aspects of the school's operation. They are the leaders responsible in providing leadership in the development and implementation of all educational programs and projects in the school. They play a vital role in achieving the government's aim to provide quality basic education.

Level Of Supervisory Skills Of The Principals

This part discusses the level of supervisory skills of the principals as perceived by the respondent groups. It presents the level of supervisory skills as assessed by the principals themselves and by the teachers in terms of curriculum and instructional supervision; organization and personnel management; planning, assessing, and reporting teaching learning outcomes; school plant, resources and facilities management; personal, social growth and professional development; and school, community linkages and public relation.

Curriculum and Instructional Supervision

This study investigated the supervisory practices of school principals. Specifically, it explored the process of the primary responsibilities among school administrators such as checking of the daily lesson plan or lesson log, the way how the instructional materials are being used and effectively maximized inside the classroom, the identification of the different challenges in delivering the instructions and how these challenges are augmented and the scaffolding process of guiding the teachers in improving classroom management.

It can be gleaned that the results of this study highlighted the supervisory skills of the school administrators in terms of curriculum and instructional supervision having the highest weighted mean of 3.55.

These were interpreted as proficient as validated and responded by the teachers. This means that school principal was able to successfully guide and help the teachers in terms of the instruction and curriculum were communicated inside the classroom in accurate and efficient way.

However, in coordinating with the officials from the district and division department, it construed the weighted mean of 3.42 and interpreted as proficient in implementing the various programs and projects from the department to the school. Although the weighted mean may provide a proficient result, it cannot deny the fact that the school principal lacks the way how the objectives, the right method for the specific lesson, the alignment of the different learning activities and the maximizing of appropriate resources to be forwarded to the learners. These observations are crucial in increasing the academic performance of the learners.

Table 3. *Curriculum and Instructional Supervision*

<i>Curriculum and Instructional Supervision</i>	<i>Principal</i>		<i>Teacher</i>	
	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Des.</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Des.</i>
1. Coordinates with the District/ Division offices in the implementation of DepEd programs and projects.	3.5	Proficient	3.42	Proficient
2. Guides teachers deliver accurate and updated content knowledge using appropriate methodologies, approaches and strategies.	3.55	Proficient	3.14	Moderately Proficient
3. Helps teachers select, prepare and utilize available technology and other instructional materials appropriate to the learners and the learning objectives.	2.7	Moderately Proficient	2.72	Moderately Proficient
4. Assists teachers align the lesson objectives, teaching methods, learning activities and instructional materials or resources appropriate to the learners.	2.3	Slightly Proficient	2.17	Slightly Proficient
5. Holds post teaching conference to evaluate the efficiency of the teachers and provide proper mentoring every after-class observation.	2.7	Moderately Proficient	2.34	Slightly Proficient
Overall	2.95	Moderately Proficient	2.76	Moderately Proficient

Legend: 4.20-5.0 (Highly Proficient), 3.40-4.19 (Proficient), 2.60-3.39 (Moderately Proficient) 1.80-2.59 (Slightly Proficient), 1.0-1.79 (Not Proficient)

Moreover, the study found that holding post-teaching conferences to evaluate teaching efficiency every after-class observation was also not given proper attention by the principals. These issues are critical in the teaching- learning process and require immediate and proper attention to uplift the level of performance of the teachers in the learning process.

The result explained that based on the principals' perception, they were proficient in guiding teachers, and they had highly coordinated with the District and Division offices in the implementation of programs and projects.

The results of this study are in line with previous research's suggestions. According to Lictao's (2007) advice, principals should effectively and efficiently manage the school and create the best possible environment for teachers to utilize their initiative, creativity, and invention. Similar to this, Aycardo (2004) advised school administrators to oversee and offer a learning environment that promotes whole cognitive development.

It is the goal of the Department of Education that every teacher will become not only efficient but also effective. It is in this mission that today, a lot of training's and seminars are being conducted to improve and develop the craft of each mentor in school. The Department fully understand that everything rises and falls on the teacher's capability to bring learning at the heart of every pupil.

Training's and seminars on ICT, new methods and techniques in teachings, orientations on the K-12 Curriculum, Values Formation Seminars and the likes are being held in different parts of the country so as to prepare all the teachers in globalization. Their attendance to these seminars will help create an effective learning environment, improve teaching-learning situations, keep updated on modern instructional devices and inspire them to become better teachers in the modern world. Since the department is offering free training's and seminars, teachers must grab this opportunity for self- improvement.

The School heads, district supervisors make actual observations of the teacher performance on the classroom setting. Principals display extensive content knowledge and pedagogy with evidence of continuing pursuit to update such and search for best practices.

In conclusion, this study emphasizes the importance of effective supervisory practices in curriculum and instructional supervision. To develop not only efficient but also effective teachers is only of the priorities of the department. Thus, principals should take proactive steps to provide the necessary support and guidance to help teachers improve their instructional practices and achieve their full potential.

Organization and Personnel Management

This study aims to examine the administrative practices of school principals in delegating duties, upholding discipline, training teachers in auxiliary services, and promoting growth and development within the organization. These procedures are essential for creating an environment that is favorable to learning, upholds the honor of the teaching profession, and respects the rights of all staff members.

Table 4 illustrates the results of the study on the school principal manage and organize the personnel in the school. The highest weighted mean score of 2.85, interpreted as moderately proficient, was obtained to let the teachers realize the importance of the right personal and professional attributes wherein the morale and dignity of the teachers are preserved. The principals received great marks for their ability to deal with behavioral issues immediately and with respect for the rights of teachers and other staff members.

Table 4. Organization and Personnel Management
Organization and Personnel Management

	<i>Principal</i>		<i>Teacher</i>	
	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Des.</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Des.</i>
1. Displays at all time a consistently high level of performance skills, abilities, initiatives and productivity.	2.3	Slightly Proficient	2.33	Slightly Proficient
2. Gives recognition to deserving teachers and recommends for scholarships and promotions.	2.65	Moderately Proficient	2.62	Moderately Proficient
3. Develops and organize in-service training programs for teachers and provides continuous and effective professional development.	2.35	Slightly Proficient	2.44	Slightly Proficient
4. Inspires teachers to exemplify personal and professional qualities that preserve the dignity of teaching profession.	2.85	Moderately Proficient	2.68	Moderately Proficient
5. Handles behavioral problems quickly and with due respect to teachers and other personnel rights.	2.85	Moderately Proficient	2.76	Moderately Proficient
Overall	2.6	Slightly Proficient	2.57	Slightly Proficient

It is evident from these findings that effective administrative practices are essential for promoting a positive school culture and ensuring the success of both teachers and students. By delegating responsibilities, maintaining discipline, and promoting growth and development, principals can create a supportive environment that fosters learning and development. Additionally, recognizing teacher talent and potential and observing transparency in school policy can improve teacher morale and promote accountability within the organization.

On the other hand, the supervisory skill on displaying at all time a consistently high level of performance skills, abilities, initiatives and productivity obtained the lowest weighted mean of 2.3 and verbally interpreted only as skilled as assessed by the teachers.

The result also implied that the teacher respondents did not receive consistent high level in their daily undertakings and the principals should look forward on the performance of his/her teachers so that proper recommendation for performance skills, abilities, initiatives and productivity is given importance. This finding is parallel with the recommendation of Jabinas (2005) that to improve principals' supervisory skills, DepEd officials should provide in-service training with emphasis on the enhancement of school administrators competencies in school management and leadership. Public School administrators need to strengthen their own school capacities in terms of teachers' instructional skills along content, instructional and communication and integrate these skills as a component of in-service trainings for teachers.

Planning, Assessing and Reporting Teaching Learning Outcomes

It refers to the way the school heads use the DepEd policies in making supervisory skills in consulting the district supervisor in planning, in involving the teaching force in planning and prioritizing teaching learning outcomes.

Table 5. Planning, Assessing, and Reporting Teaching Learning Outcomes

<i>Planning, Assessing, and Reporting Teaching Learning Outcomes</i>	<i>Principal</i>		<i>Teacher</i>	
	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Des.</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Des.</i>
1. Develops and use a variety of appropriate assessment strategies to monitor and evaluate teaching and learning.	2.7	Moderately Proficient	2.6	Slightly Proficient
2. Provides timely and accurate feedback to teachers to encourage them to reflect on and monitor their own teaching/ professional growth.	2.8	Moderately Proficient	2.71	Moderately Proficient
3. Keeps accurate records, grades and performance level of learners and teachers.	2.9	Moderately Proficient	2.75	Moderately Proficient
4. Develops and utilizes creative and appropriate instructional planning.	2.7	Moderately Proficient	2.67	Moderately Proficient
5. Establishes and maintains consistent standards of teachers and learner's behavior.	1.9	Slightly Proficient	2.07	Slightly Proficient
Overall	2.6	Slightly Proficient	2.57	Slightly Proficient

As shown in table 5, the supervisory skills in the aspect how the planning, evaluating and reporting the intended learning outcomes construed the highest mean rating of 2.9 verbally interpreted as moderately proficient as perceived by the principals themselves. While keeping accurate records, grades and performance levels of learners and teachers obtained a mean rating of 2.75 verbally interpreted as moderately proficient as assessed by the teachers.

The result emphasized that the principals perceived that they display at all times a high level of skills, abilities and attributes, initiatives and productivity in the development and use of variety of appropriate assessment strategies to monitor and evaluate teaching and learning, and establishment and maintenance of consistent standards of teachers and learners and keeping accurate records grades and performance level of teachers and learners. It also implied that the supervisory skills of the principals often exceed expectations based on standards and display high level of related skills, abilities, initiatives and productivity, exceeding requirements in many of the supervisory skills in the development and utilization of creative and appropriate instructional planning.

In the overall result, both principal and teachers’ perception had the same interpretation which is slightly proficient in terms of supervisory skills in aspect of planning, assessing and reporting teaching learning outcomes. The result implied that both respondents agreed that this area needs enhancement in order to produce better outcome.

This is consistent with Adriano’s (2010) study, which found that the managerial abilities of Rodriguez II district principals in terms of how the teachers plan, organize, lead, and control the situation inside the classroom which were rated with High Extent.

According to Santos’ study from 2007, principals perform to a high extent in terms of planning and organizing, but only rated moderate extent in terms of leading and controlling. According to the results of her study, there was no discernible difference in how the teacher and the principals themselves perceived the level of how the school administrators are planning, leading, and controlling various variables that affect the teaching- learning process.

Education is a never-ending process. It doesn’t stop after earning a degree and starting a career. Through continuing education, career-minded individuals can constantly improve their skills and become more proficient at their jobs. In the field of K-12 education administration, it is particularly important for school administrators to encourage teachers to pursue professional development, not only to ensure the best learning outcomes for their students but also to be more effective and satisfied in various other aspects of their work.

Educational technology, school district guidelines and curriculum standards are constantly changing, making it challenging for teachers to keep up with trends and best practices in the field. Professional development transforms teachers into better and more apt educators by enabling them to create relevant and tailored course instructions for today’s students.

When educators discover new teaching strategies through professional development, they are able to go back to the classroom and make changes to their lecture styles and curricula to better suit the needs of their students. However, these changes are hard to evaluate because they are typically implemented gradually. Professional development for teachers makes them more efficient in their presentations and course evaluations by exposing educators to new delivery methods, evaluation styles and record-keeping strategies.

Good teachers become great teachers by going beyond the call of duty and beyond the textbook. To do this, he or she must continue their education. There are conferences, workshops, and continuing education that could give the teacher that extra help in technology for their students. There are online workshops, and classes that teachers could attend as well as on-site workshop and classes.

Administrators should encourage their teachers to continue their education as well as make opportunities available for them to do so. Moreover, administrators and districts should offer to either pay or help pay for the classes and workshops. There are workshops on how to integrate technology into the classroom and how to make it cross curricular.

School Plant, Resources and Facilities Management

It refers to how the school principal maintains and improves the school site, housing operation, upkeep and extension of the existing plant to promote efficient instruction and to meet the requirement of space and safety.

The resources of any institution are people, land, machines, buildings, technology, materials and money. These are the primary components of an organization needed for production and operation. The outputs are efficient services, such that productive resources constitute the most important areas of management. Human capital, financial and physical resources should be properly and efficiently utilized to be able to achieve organizational goals and objectives.

Table 6. School Plant, Resources and Facilities Management

<i>School Plant, Resources and Facilities Management</i>	<i>Principal</i>		<i>Teacher</i>	
	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Des.</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Des.</i>
1. Taps government, non-government agencies for provisions of school facilities and equipment.	3.25	Moderately Proficient	2.95	Moderately Proficient
2. Assist teacher with maximum utilization of the school surroundings and equipment without destroying them.	2.7	Moderately Proficient	2.71	Moderately Proficient
3. Conducts fund-raising campaigns to improve and upgrade the school’s service centers.	2.6	Slightly Proficient	2.54	Slightly Proficient
4. Maintains an accepting, permissive, and non-threatening school atmosphere.	2.1	Slightly Proficient	2.1	Slightly Proficient
5. Observes transparency in money matters, school policy, activities and projects.	1.9	Slightly Proficient	1.87	Slightly Proficient
Overall	2.51	Slightly Proficient	2.41	Slightly Proficient

Having properly managed facilities is important for saving on costs. Managing your equipment and premises will make maintenance issues fewer and far between, helping you save on costs significantly. It also allows you to focus more on prevention rather than treatment, since you can deal with problems before they arise. The regular maintenance of buildings could include assessing electrical wiring conditions within the office building and determining if repairs are needed. Facilities managers are also in charge of maintaining hygiene standards. This includes the disposal of waste, sanitation of the office building and regularly scheduled cleaning.

As shown in table 6, the aspect of taps government, non-government agencies for provisions of school facilities and equipment’s respectively received the highest mean rating of 3.25 and 2.95 verbally interpreted as moderately proficient as perceived by the principals themselves and the teacher respondents.

On the other hand, two of the aspects were rated very low by the teachers with a rated mean of 2 and 1.87 verbally interpreted as slightly proficient were maintains an accepting, permissive, school atmosphere and observes transparency in money matters, school policy, activities and projects respectively.

The result emphasized that two of the five items in aspect of school plant, resources and facilities management were rated very low by the teacher respondents these were maintains an accepting permissive, and non-threatening school atmosphere and observing transparency in money matters, school policies, activities and projects.

This implied that the principals should maintain a high level of respect with regards to money matters since this is the most sensitive and most crucial focal point in school supervision.

The study of Wiles in 2000 supports these findings when he pointed out that the basic function of supervision is to improve the learning situation of children by providing appropriate educational facilities and equipments that will enhance and provide quality education among learners. If any administrator in his supervisory capacity does not contribute to effective learning in the school, his existence as such cannot be justified.

Likewise, Marcos (2006) recommended that School Administrators should perform the management functions effectively and efficiently in order to utilized supplies and materials properly and religiously. He further recommended that school principals should ask support from local and non-government organizations to help meet the needs of the school especially on improving the physical outlook of the school.

Personal, Social Growth and Professional Development

Personal, Social Growth and Professional Development one of the essential supervisory skills of school principals are the personal development of the teachers, the social aspect, and most importantly the professional development in the field of educational leadership. This includes the duty to organize conferences and meetings for teachers, to give them access to training and the seminars, to support the personal growth of teachers, and to ensure that the skills they pick up at workshops and conferences are put to use.

Table 7 presents an enlightening insight into the assessment of personal, social, and professional development skills. Both principals and teachers rated the manifestation of personal qualities, such as enthusiasm, flexibility, caring attitude, and collegiality, as the highest skill with a mean of 4.55 and 4.51, respectively. The data demonstrates that principals have executed their supervisory function with effectiveness and dedication, especially in areas related to personal, social, and professional development.

Table 7. *Personal, Social Growth and Professional Development*

<i>Personal, Social Growth and Professional Development</i>	<i>Principal</i>		<i>Teacher</i>	
	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Des.</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Des.</i>
1. Manifests personal qualities like enthusiasm, flexibility, caring attitude, collegiality among others.	4.55	Highly Proficient	4.51	Highly Proficient
2. Improves supervisory performance based on feedback from colleagues, superiors and others.	4.4	Highly Proficient	4.42	Highly Proficient
3. Updates oneself with recent developments in education through readings, attendance in continuing professional education and or training and seminars.	4.55	Highly Proficient	4.5	Highly Proficient
4. Demonstrates educational philosophy of school supervision.	3.45	Proficient	3.64	Proficient
5. Maintains appropriate appearance and decorum at all times.	2.95	Moderately Proficient	3.1	Moderately Proficient
Overall	3.98	Proficient	4.03	Proficient

This finding suggest that principals have exhibited a commendable level of skills, abilities, attributes, initiatives, and productivity. Specifically, the skills displayed in this aspect were beyond the expected level of proficiency, as evidenced by their outstanding performance. Such a result not only highlights the importance of personal, social, and professional development skills in the educational setting but also underscores the significance of exemplary leadership in promoting teacher growth and development.

Similar idea by Schermerhorn in 2008 that this essential skill of administrators is categorized into three such as technical, human, and conceptual skills that tend to vary by level of managerial responsibility. Technical skill is the ability to use special proficiency or expertise to perform particular task. These skills are acquired through formal education and further develop by training and job experience. It is the ability to apply expertise to perform task with proficiency. Human skill is the ability to work well in cooperation with other people. It emerges in the workplace as a spirit of trust, enthusiasm, and genuine involvement in interpersonal relationships.

A manager with good human skills will have a high degree of self-awareness and a capacity to understand or empathize with the feelings of others. In addition to these managerial skills, he added the emotional intelligence which is according to him, is the important aspect to human skills. It is the ability to manage oneself and relationships effectively. Indeed, human skills and emotional intelligence

are consistently important across all managerial levels.

It's easy for teachers to become burdened by the grind of teaching. Professional development gives them an opportunity to step out of their routine they get to be the student instead of the teacher. This keeps educators engaged because they feel like they are receiving the professional help they need to be better teachers. After all, professional development nurtures the talents of teachers who aspire to take on educational leadership positions, and teachers must learn from other experienced leaders to become effective future leaders themselves.

Implementing professional education development has benefits for both teachers and students, but most importantly, it helps teachers become better educators and develop into competent future school administrators.

The state of North Carolina understands the importance of continuing education for its teachers and school leaders. Charlottes (2019) stated that Public Schools of North Carolina has implemented a NC Professional Development Office that focuses on providing schools with leadership, resources, technical assistance, and consultative services in related to professional development with improved student achievement as the end goal. The site lists various resources for administrators and teachers to develop skills and learn best practices according to the latest standards in the education field.

One development option for teachers who are interested in taking on a leadership role and pursuing school administrator certification is an educational leadership master's degree. Charlottes (2019) also stated that MA in Educational Leadership program offers the personal support and leadership skills teachers need to stay current in the field while becoming better educators and preparing to become effective school head.

In conclusion, this study emphasizes the crucial role that personal, social, and professional development plays in the supervisory skills of principals. Principals who actively engage in promoting and implementing these skills can foster a positive work environment and contribute to the growth and development of their teachers. Further, these areas demonstrate a high level of leadership proficiency, which benefits not only the teachers but also the overall quality of education.

School, Community Linkages and Public Relation

In an effort to better the conditions for teaching and learning, this study investigates how school administrators connect with and access the community. Establishing linkages of the various internal and external stakeholders and institutions pave the way to providing meaningful learning experiences among the learners. It becomes a shared responsibility of helping one another in bringing forth the fostering of the children into the building block of this country. Creating a difference is indeed a responsibility of all constituents in the society and this can be tracked back on how the different institutions are helping a school to produce holistic graduates.

In this study, the supervisory skills in the aspect of school- community linkages and public relations were assessed through a survey conducted among principals and teachers in public elementary and secondary schools in the District of Dumanjug II.

A school is not an independent or isolated entity; it operates in a social context, an important component of which is the local community. The school draws its students/pupils on the local community and depends on the community for much of its financial and social support. The community exercises its power over the school primarily through the school board, which has the power to mandate policies and guidelines. The community also expects its influence on the school informally through parents' groups and individual contacts. Because of these factors every school head needs to develop profound understanding in maintaining and building effective school community relations (Gorton).

Table 8. School, Community Linkages and Public Relation

School, Community Linkages and Public Relation	Principal		Teacher	
	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.
1. Informs parents, learners and other stakeholders regarding school policies and procedures.	3.3	Moderately Proficient	3.06	Moderately Proficient
2. Involves the community in sharing accountability for learner's achievement.	3.25	Moderately Proficient	3.23	Moderately Proficient
3. Provides leadership in the formulation and implementation of all educational programs in school and community.	3.6	Proficient	3.36	Moderately Proficient
4. Maintains an open line communication with parents, teachers and the community.	3.2	Moderately Proficient	3.28	Moderately Proficient
5. Coordinates with the community and public officials for the wholesome growth and development of all pupils and other personnel in the school.	3.75	Proficient	3.44	Proficient
Overall	3.34	Moderately Proficient	3.23	Moderately Proficient

Linkages between these two institutions are a proven and effective way for schools to expand what they can offer to children and provide more meaningful learning experiences making a real difference in the lives of children, families, and communities.

As shown in table 8, the supervisory skills in aspect of school, community linkages and public relation with the highest rated mean of

3.75 and 3.44 verbally interpreted as proficient as assessed by the principals themselves and by the teachers was coordinates with the community and public officials for the wholesome growth and development of all pupils and other personnel in the school.

School community relationship is a mutual understanding through which the school and the community link with each other for the achievement of goals of the community and school too. School is a social organization functions properly on the effective interrelationship within it and with its associate communities.

On the other hand, the least rated skill with a rated mean of 3.2 and 3.06 verbally interpreted as moderately proficient as assessed by the principals themselves and by the teachers were maintains an open line of communication with parents, teachers and the community and coordinates with the community and public officials for the wholesome growth and development of all pupils and other personnel in the school and informs parents, learners and other stakeholders regarding school policies and procedures.

This study emphasizes that principals have made efforts to involve the community in achieving a high degree of performance among pupils and other personnel in the school. This connotes the value placed on school and community relations. Pacelo's study in 2007 supports the data of this study, recommending that school administrators ensure teachers and the community are aware of matters regarding school-based management. This awareness will enable them to understand their roles and what contribution they can give to improve the school.

The findings indicate that the principals in public elementary and secondary schools in District of Dumanjug II were moderately proficient in managing and supervising the schools. However, this implies that the principals need an enhancement training program since their respective teachers were not fully satisfied with their supervisory skills. Teachers' perceptions about their principals' supervisory skills are crucial factor in serving as a check and balance to determine whether the principal is fulfilling their job. The result also highlights that many aspects of supervisory skills among principals were not satisfactory to the teacher respondents, and it requires immediate fixing through an enhancement training design.

The partnership may involve use of school, facilities and equipment, sharing other resources, collaborative fund raising and grant applications, volunteer assistance, mentoring and training from professionals and others with special expertise, information sharing and dissemination, networking, recognition and public relations, shared responsibility for planning, implementation and evaluation of programs and services, expanding opportunities for internships, jobs, recreation and building a sense of community.

Encourage community use of school facilities: Often the school building sit empty after the end of the normal school day. Encouraging non-profit community groups to use the facilities is not only good use of resources but also provides opportunities for the schools to get involved in community projects. School resources are very important in promoting school community relationship. According to Bakwai (2013) some of these resources which can be used in promoting school community relationship and the importance of effective school community linkages and public relations in improving the teaching and learning situation. It is vital to establish good relationships and communication among all internal and external stakeholders who are pertinent in making progress in the school. These areas require an enhancement training design for the principals to be more proficient in managing and supervising schools. They can be allowed to be used by the communities when school closes or is on holidays. Egbezor (2005) noted that the classrooms are used for adult literacy activities nationwide, for public health activities like immunizations, public enlightenment exercises, in emergency epidemic situations and school building are converted into make shift hospitals. School buildings are also put into use during voting exercises. This will help establish good relationship with the community.

The action team approach to partnerships guides the work of educators by restructuring staff development to mean colleagues working together and with parents to develop, implement, evaluate, and continue to improve practices of partnership. This is less a dose of in-service education than it is an active form of developing staff talents and capacities. The teachers, administrators, and others on the action team become the experts on this topic for their school. Their work in this area can be supported by various federal, state, and local funding programs as a clear investment in staff development for overall school reform. Indeed, the action team approach as outlined can be applied to any or all-important topics on a school improvement agenda. It need not be restricted to the pursuit of successful partnerships. It is important to note that the development of partnership programs would be easier if educators came to their schools prepared to work productively with families and communities. Courses or classes are needed in preservice teacher education and in advanced degree programs for teachers and administrators to help them define their professional work in terms of partnerships.

Today, most educators enter schools without an understanding of family backgrounds, concepts of caring, the framework of partnerships, or the other basics that are discussed here.

Thus, most principals and district leaders are not prepared to guide and lead their staffs in developing strong school and classroom practices that inform and involve families. Most teachers and administrators also are unprepared to understand, design, implement, or evaluate good practices of partnership with the families of their students.

Summary Table for Level of Supervisory Skills

This part presents the summary of the level of supervisory skills of the principals. It is observed on the table that the over-all mean rating of the principals on their supervisory skills in aspects of curriculum and instructional supervision, organization and personnel management, planning, assessing, and reporting teaching learning outcomes; school plant, resources and facilities management;

personal, social growth and professional development and school, community linkages and public relation were 2.99 interpreted as moderately proficient. While the over-all mean rating of the teachers in the different aspects were 2.92 with an interpretation of moderately proficient.

Table 9. Summary Table for Level of Supervisory Skills of the Principals

Supervisory Skills	Principal		Teacher	
	Mean	Des.	Mean	Des.
Curriculum and Instructional Supervision	2.95	Moderately Proficient	2.76	Moderately Proficient
Organization and Personnel Management	2.6	Moderately Proficient	2.57	Slightly Proficient
Planning, assessing and Reporting Teaching Learning Outcomes	2.6	Moderately Proficient	2.56	Slightly Proficient
School Plant, Resources and Facilities Management	2.51	Slightly Proficient	2.41	Slightly Proficient
Personal, Social Growth and Professional Development	3.98	Proficient	4.03	Proficient
School, Community Linkages and Public Relation	3.34	Moderately Proficient	3.23	Moderately Proficient
Overall	2.99	Moderately Proficient	2.92	Moderately Proficient

The findings indicated that the principals in public elementary and secondary school in District of Dumanjug II were moderately proficient in managing and supervising the schools. This implied that the principals need enhancement training program because it's obvious that their respective teachers were not fully satisfied with their supervisory skills.

Teachers' perception about their principals' supervisory skills is a crucial factor in order to serve as check and balance whether the principal is really fulfilling their job. And based on the result, there were many aspects of supervisory skills among principals, where teacher respondents felt that they were not satisfied about it. This problem has to be fixed immediately through an "Enhancement Training Design".

Test Of Significant Difference

Table 10, presented on the following page, displays the mean rank, p-value, alpha, decision, and interpretation of the supervisory skills of the principals. The significant difference between the teacher's perception and the school principal's skills in supervision manifested in this study.

The calculated p- values on how the curriculum and instruction were supervise, the organization on how people are being organized, the process of reporting, planning, and assessing the outcomes of the teaching and learning process, the different installed school plants and infrastructures, the growth and development of the teachers both personally and professionally, and the linkages built among the different stakeholders garnered 0.213, 0.892, 0.356, 0.261, 0.357, and 0.881, respectively, with probability values below the .05 level of significance, leading to the conclusion that the findings are not statistically significant.

As depicted on the Table, Curriculum and Instructional Supervision revealed a p-value of 0.213 lesser than the alpha which is 0.05 failed to reject Ho which means that the difference between the ratings resulting with a verbal interpretation of not significant. The results of this study are in line with previous research's suggestions. Similar to this, Aycardo (2004) advised school administrators to oversee and offer a learning environment that promotes whole cognitive development.

Table 10. Significant Difference between Principals and Teachers' Perceptions

Parameters	Respondents	Mean Rank	P- Value	Decision	Interpre- tation
Curriculum and Instructional Supervision	Principals	22.80	0.213	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
	Teachers	18.20			
Organization and Personnel Management	Principals	20.75	0.892	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
	Teachers	20.25			
Planning, assessing and Reporting Teaching Learning Outcomes	Principals	22.20	0.356	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
	Teachers	18.80			
School Plant, Resources and Facilities Management	Principals	22.58	0.261	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
	Teachers	18.43			
Personal, Social Growth and Professional Development	Principals	18.80	0.357	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant
	Teachers	22.20			
School, Community Linkages and Public Relation	Principals	20.23	0.881	Failed to reject Ho	Not Significant

Alpha: 0.05

Statistically, there is no significant difference (0.213, 0.892, 0.356, 0.261, 0.351, 0.881) between the principals' and teachers' perception towards the principals' supervisory skills.

Organization and Personnel Management obtained a p-value of 0.892 lesser than the alpha which is 0.05 failed to reject Ho which means that the difference between the ratings resulting with a verbal interpretation of not significant. This finding is parallel with the recommendation of Jabinas in his study in 2005 that to improve principals' supervisory skills, DepEd officials should provide in-service training with emphasis on the enhancement of school administrators competencies in school management and leadership.

Planning, Assessing and Reporting Teaching Learning Outcomes, obtained a p-value of 0.356 lesser than the alpha which is 0.05 failed to reject H_0 resulting with a verbal interpretation of not significant. According to Santos' study from 2007, principals perform to a high extent in terms of planning and organizing, but only rated moderate extent in terms of leading and controlling. According to the results of her study, there was no discernible difference in how the teacher and the principals themselves perceived the level of how the school administrators are planning, leading, and controlling various variables that affect the teaching- learning process.

School Plant, Resources and Facilities Management, obtained a p-value of 0.261 lesser than the alpha which is 0.05 resulting with a verbal interpretation of not significant. Likewise, Marcos in his study in 2006 recommended that School Administrators should perform the management functions effectively and efficiently in order to utilized supplies and materials properly and religiously. He further recommended that school principals should ask support from local and non-government organizations to help meet the needs of the school especially on improving the physical outlook of the school.

Personal, Social Growth and Professional Development, obtained a p-value of 0.357 lesser than the alpha which is 0.05 resulting with a verbal interpretation of not significant. Similar idea by Schermerhorn in 2008 that this essential skill of administrators is categorized into three such as technical, human, and conceptual skills that tend to vary by level of managerial responsibility. Technical skill is the ability to use special proficiency or expertise to perform particular task. These skills are acquired through formal education and further develop by training and job experience.

School, Community Linkages and Public Relation, obtained a p-value of 0.881 lesser than the alpha which is 0.05 resulting with a verbal interpretation of not significant. School community relationship is a mutual understanding through which the school and the community link with each other for the achievement of goals of the community and school too. School is a social organization functions properly on the effective interrelationship within it and with its associate communities.

Test Of Significant Relationship

An issue in a school affects the community likewise to what happens in the community affects school. This implies that the community builds its schools likewise to the schools (Sidhu, 2007). Therefore, school relation with the community is mutually interdependence.

As presented in table 11, Age and Supervisory Skill obtained a p-value of 0.032, indicating a significant difference in the level of supervisory skills of the principals with respect to their age with an interpretation of not significant. The findings on this criterion were supported by Austria in his study in 2000 when he revealed in his findings that age was significantly related to performance on the administrative of significance and supervisory practices of the school heads.

Table 11. *Significant Relationship on the Level of Supervisory Skills of the Principals*

<i>Parameters</i>	<i>X²- Value</i>	<i>Cramer's V- Value</i>	<i>Int.</i>	<i>P- Value</i>	<i>Decision</i>	<i>Int.</i>
Age and Supervisory Skill	6.89	0.6	Strong	0.032	Reject H_0	Significant
Gender and Supervisory Skill	0.21	0.105	Weak	0.9	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
Civil Status and Supervisory Skill	5.66	0.493	Moderate	0.226	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
Educational Attainment and Supervisory Skill	5.26	0.326	Moderate	0.511	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
Academic Rank and Supervisory Skill	4.41	0.292	Weak	0.353	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
Position Held and Supervisory Skill	6.37	0.409	Moderate	0.173	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
Training Attendance and Supervisory Skill	4.56	0.285	Weak	0.335	Failed to Reject	Not Significant
Managerial Experience and Supervisory Skill	8.21	0.42	Moderate	0.084	Failed to Reject	Not Significant

On the other hand, Gender and Supervisory Skill obtained a p-value of 0.9, resulting in the acceptance of the null hypothesis with a verbal interpretation of not significant. This implies that age had a great effect on how the principals perform their duties in curriculum and oversight of instruction; and preparing, evaluating, and summarizing teaching- learning results. The younger the principal is, the greater effort is evident in performing their supervisory skills.

However, Civil Status and Supervisory Skill obtained a p-value of 0.226 resulting to the acceptance of the null hypothesis with a verbal interpretation of not significant. While Aquino in her study in 2002 confirmed the findings on the four items in this criterion when she elicited in her findings that, there was no significant relationship between the respondents' perception on the level of supervisory practices of the school heads. There are plenty of examples where leaders have become successful despite their civil status and career choices.

Educational Attainment and Supervisory Skill obtained a p-value of 0.511 resulting to the acceptance of the null hypothesis with a verbal interpretation of not significant. Experienced leaders are more likely to have developed organizational, time management, and planning skills over the course of their careers. They're also more stable and reliable and have been shown to have solid decision-making skills.

Academic Rank and Supervisory Skill obtained a p-value of 0.353 resulting to the acceptance of the null hypothesis with a verbal interpretation of not significant. Skills of good leadership can be defined how their way of dealing with people and organizing their thoughts in addressing the needs of a particular organization. Leaders should constantly be updated on how to deal with people. As the

culture in a particular institution such as a school, one must realize on how to bring people together in order to realize the vision, mission, and goals established by the department.

Position Held and Supervisory Skill obtained a p-value of 0.173 resulting to the acceptance of the null hypothesis with a verbal interpretation of not significant. In a school, the school principal should be sensitive in communicating with the teachers, students and parents. Listening to them is very important in understanding their side. When conflict arise, school principal should know what to do in order to stop it. When effective communication is employed, harmony and peace will be sustained not just in school but anywhere where diversity is present.

Training Attendance and Supervisory Skill obtained a p-value of 0.335 resulting to the acceptance of the null hypothesis with a verbal interpretation of not significant. Leaders can truly make a difference in the teaching and learning process when transformational and desired attitude are present. The decision-making skills should be one of the utmost priorities in developing an efficient and effective leader. Leaders are made and they are not born.

Managerial Experience and Supervisory Skill obtained a p-value of 0.084 resulting to the acceptance of the null hypothesis with a verbal interpretation of not significant. There are many qualities that makes a great leader. Experience, commitment, and knowledge of your industry are at the top of the list. But it's important to remember that neither age nor experience alone defines a leader.

Conclusions

Based on the findings, it can be concluded that the level of supervisory skills of the principals is viewed as moderately effective based on the principals' perspective but it is viewed as moderately low based on the teachers' perspective. Therefore, supervision is a critical component of any organization or profession, providing guidance, support, and oversight to ensure effective performance and continuous improvement of teachers' professionalism.

With the foregoing findings, it is suggested that principals must continue to improve their supervisory skills and must indulge into further studies and trainings to bridge any gaps between their self – assessment and the assessment of their subordinates which can ultimately benefit the entire school community. Hence, an “ENHANCEMENT TRAINING DESIGN” is recommended.

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